

APPROXIMATIONS FOR FULLY ISOTROPIC LAMINATE CONFIGURATIONS (COUPLED LAMINATE DERIVATIVES)

C. B. York
University of Glasgow
Department of Aerospace Engineering
c.york@aero.gla.ac.uk

SUMMARY

A search strategy is described for identifying coupled laminate configurations, with generic angle- and cross-ply combinations, closely approximating fully isotropic behaviour. However, double-angle-ply and multi-angle-ply laminates from the literature are also considered for the purposes of comparison.

Keywords: Fully coupled laminates; Lamination Parameters; Approximate, Equivalent and Fully Isotropic Laminates.

Introduction

This article follows recent work¹ detailing a search strategy for identifying laminate configurations, closely approximating isotropic behaviour. The resulting configurations were derivatives from a definitive list² of **F**ully uncoupled **O**rthotropic **L**aminates (**FOLs**) with up to 21 plies, containing exact configurations for **E**xtensionally **I**sotropic **L**aminates (**EILs**) and **F**ully **I**sotropic **L**aminates (**FILs**), i.e. sub-sets of the definitive list of **FOLs**. Approximations to the **FIL** are of interest because very few laminate configurations satisfy the **FIL** condition exactly; all are 18-ply laminates within the range of thin laminates considered, i.e. with up to 21 plies.

Standard ply angle configurations, $\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$, were adopted in the previous work. Only the exact **FIL** configuration maintains the fully uncoupled flexural (and membrane) stiffness condition for off-axis material alignment; coupling terms are introduced in all other (**FOL**) sequences. Approximations were therefore characterized in terms of their proximity to the lamination parameters describing a **FIL** configuration. The proximity criteria applied, related both to the laminate stiffness properties and the corresponding thermal/mechanical deformations with respect to the **FIL** or equivalent **FIL**.

The scope for broadening the number of possible configurations, and/or reducing the number of plies in the laminate, is investigated in the current article by developing a similar search strategy for coupled laminates, with standard ply angle configurations, $\pm\theta^\circ/0^\circ/90^\circ$. Additionally, double-angle-ply and multi-angle-ply laminates from the literature are also considered for the purposes of comparison.

Background

There are a number of practical applications for configurations closely approximating the fully isotropic condition. These include large diameter mirrors for space-based reflector telescopes, which require low mass and low coefficient of thermal expansion mirrors, both of which are met by carbon fibre composite laminates. Hence,

configurations for thinner laminates satisfying these requirements continue to be of interest³⁻⁶.

Paradies³ demonstrated that bending isotropy could be closely approximated in double-angle-ply, fully uncoupled, orthotropic laminates without necessarily satisfying in-plane isotropy, which is contrary to the procedure for obtaining exact **FIL** configurations. In fact, the solution presented was based on a fully uncoupled **EIL** with $\pi/4$ isotropy, AC 30: $[\mp/O/\bullet_2/O/\mp_2/\bullet/O_2/\bullet/\mp]_T$ derived elsewhere², in which the cross-ply (O/\bullet) were replaced by a second set of angle plies, giving $[\mp\alpha/\mp\beta]_S/[\mp\alpha/\mp\beta]_S$. The extensional isotropy was destroyed during this transition, but the double-angle-ply configuration that resulted was shown to possess bending stiffness properties closely approximating the **FIL** with two different combinations of angle-ply, i.e. $[\mp27/\pm74]_S/[\mp27/\mp74]_S$ and $[\mp63/\pm16]_S/[\mp63/\mp16]_S$.

Other examples of approximate laminate configurations were presented by Fukunaga⁷, Grédiac⁸ and Vannucci⁹. Fukunaga⁷ obtained exact solutions for a 40-ply laminate and approximations for six 20-ply configurations; the latter were based on symmetric combinations of four different angle-ply pairs, e.g. $[\pm66.94/\pm20.31/\pm42.1/\pm78.9]_S$. Grédiac⁸ and Vannucci⁹ obtained very close approximations to a **FIL** with 12 plies using optimization strategies, leading to configurations with seemingly random combinations of (non-integer) angle-ply orientations, containing residual (non-zero) coupling ($B_{ij} \neq 0$) terms. Grédiac⁸ additionally considered the effect of rounding, e.g. to the nearest integer $[0/59/107/129/50/130/178/78/179/21/69/128]_T$, to explore the fibre alignment sensitivity on the laminate stiffness properties; **ABD** matrices were presented for each case. Paradies³ and Fukunaga⁷ presented polar plots to demonstrate the degree of proximity to the **FIL**; the latter supported by experimental data.

The question is not so much how close the stiffness properties are to the **FIL**, but rather how close the mechanical/thermal behaviour relates to the **FIL**. For the uncoupled laminates presented previously, the behaviour was relatively self evident from the magnitude of the coupling terms from the extensional- and bending-stiffness matrices. Indeed, the stiffness and behavioural properties were shown to be approximately related by a number of simple ‘rules of thumb’. In the context of the extension presented here, the coupling matrix, may possess one of several forms, leading to highly complex behaviour; some forms of coupling being stronger than others.

Composite Mirror Construction

The application of this work to large diameter mirrors for space-based reflector telescopes was mentioned briefly but not developed. Such mirrors are typically formed by the bonding of a thin metallic surface layer to a composite laminate substrate. It should be noted however that the metallic layer has a significant effect on the behavioural properties: A fully uncoupled isotropic laminate, of the sort presented herein, with an isotropic metallic layer bonded to one outer surface possesses combined bending-extension and shear-twist couplings. The design of metallic surface coated carbon fibre substrate **FILs** may therefore require the consideration of coupled laminate configurations, in order to counteract the induced coupling effect of the metallic surface.

Search Strategy for approximate FILs

For optimum design of angle-ply laminates, lamination parameters are often preferred, since these allow the stiffness terms to be expressed as linear variables. The optimized

lamination parameters may then be matched against a corresponding set of stacking sequences with given laminate thickness $H (= n \times t)$. In the context of the non dimensional parameters for the membrane ($n, n_+, n_-, n_o, n_{\bullet}$) and flexural ($\zeta_+, \zeta_-, \zeta_o, \zeta_{\bullet}$) stiffness, presented in previous work, only four (ξ_1, ξ_2, ξ_9 and ξ_{10}) of the twelve lamination parameters were required when the material was axis-aligned. However, for coupled laminates, additional parameters ($\chi_+, \chi_-, \chi_o, \chi_{\bullet}$) are included to account for the coupling matrix, and all twelve lamination parameters must now be considered:

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_1 &= \xi_1^A = \{n_+\cos(2\theta_+) + n_-\cos(2\theta_-) + n_o\cos(2\theta_o) + n_{\bullet}\cos(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \\ \xi_2 &= \xi_2^A = \{n_+\cos(4\theta_+) + n_-\cos(4\theta_-) + n_o\cos(4\theta_o) + n_{\bullet}\cos(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \\ \xi_3 &= \xi_3^A = \{n_+\sin(2\theta_+) + n_-\sin(2\theta_-) + n_o\sin(2\theta_o) + n_{\bullet}\sin(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n \\ \xi_4 &= \xi_4^A = \{n_+\sin(4\theta_+) + n_-\sin(4\theta_-) + n_o\sin(4\theta_o) + n_{\bullet}\sin(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_5 &= \xi_1^B = \{\chi_+\cos(2\theta_+) + \chi_-\cos(2\theta_-) + \chi_o\cos(2\theta_o) + \chi_{\bullet}\cos(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^2 \\ \xi_6 &= \xi_2^B = \{\chi_+\cos(4\theta_+) + \chi_-\cos(4\theta_-) + \chi_o\cos(4\theta_o) + \chi_{\bullet}\cos(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^2 \\ \xi_7 &= \xi_3^B = \{\chi_+\sin(2\theta_+) + \chi_-\sin(2\theta_-) + \chi_o\sin(2\theta_o) + \chi_{\bullet}\sin(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^2 \\ \xi_8 &= \xi_4^B = \{\chi_+\sin(4\theta_+) + \chi_-\sin(4\theta_-) + \chi_o\sin(4\theta_o) + \chi_{\bullet}\sin(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^2\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned}\xi_9 &= \xi_1^D = \{\zeta_+\cos(2\theta_+) + \zeta_-\cos(2\theta_-) + \zeta_o\cos(2\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet}\cos(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \\ \xi_{10} &= \xi_2^D = \{\zeta_+\cos(4\theta_+) + \zeta_-\cos(4\theta_-) + \zeta_o\cos(4\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet}\cos(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \\ \xi_{11} &= \xi_3^D = \{\zeta_+\sin(2\theta_+) + \zeta_-\sin(2\theta_-) + \zeta_o\sin(2\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet}\sin(2\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3 \\ \xi_{12} &= \xi_4^D = \{\zeta_+\sin(4\theta_+) + \zeta_-\sin(4\theta_-) + \zeta_o\sin(4\theta_o) + \zeta_{\bullet}\sin(4\theta_{\bullet})\}/n^3\end{aligned}\quad (3)$$

Elements of the extensional, coupling and bending stiffness matrices are related to the lamination parameters and laminate invariants, respectively, by:

$$\begin{aligned}A_{11} &= \{U_1 + \xi_1 U_2 + \xi_2 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{12} &= A_{21} = \{-\xi_2 U_3 + U_4\} \times H \\ A_{16} &= A_{61} = \{\xi_3 U_2/2 + \xi_4 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{22} &= \{U_1 - \xi_1 U_2 + \xi_2 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{26} &= A_{62} = \{\xi_3 U_2/2 - \xi_4 U_3\} \times H \\ A_{66} &= \{-\xi_2 U_3 + U_5\} \times H\end{aligned}\quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}B_{11} &= \{\xi_5 U_2 + \xi_6 U_3\} \times H^2/4 \\ B_{12} &= B_{21} = \{-\xi_6 U_3\} \times H^2/4 \\ B_{16} &= B_{61} = \{\xi_7 U_2/2 + \xi_8 U_3\} \times H^2/4 \\ B_{22} &= \{-\xi_5 U_2 + \xi_6 U_3\} \times H^2/4 \\ B_{26} &= B_{62} = \{\xi_7 U_2/2 - \xi_8 U_3\} \times H^2/4\end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{B}_{66} = \{-\xi_6 U_3\} \times H^2/4 \quad (5)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D}_{11} &= \{U_1 + \xi_9 U_2 + \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ \mathbf{D}_{12} = \mathbf{D}_{21} &= \{U_4 - \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ \mathbf{D}_{16} = \mathbf{D}_{61} &= \{\xi_{11} U_2/2 + \xi_{12} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ \mathbf{D}_{22} &= \{U_1 - \xi_9 U_2 + \xi_{10} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ \mathbf{D}_{26} = \mathbf{D}_{62} &= \{\xi_{11} U_2/2 - \xi_{12} U_3\} \times H^3/12 \\ \mathbf{D}_{66} &= \{-\xi_{10} U_3 + U_5\} \times H^3/12 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

where the laminate invariants are calculated from the reduced stiffness terms Q_{ij} :

$$\begin{aligned} U_1 &= \{3Q_{11} + 3Q_{22} + 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\ U_2 &= \{Q_{11} - Q_{22}\}/2 \\ U_3 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\ U_4 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} + 6Q_{12} - 4Q_{66}\}/8 \\ U_5 &= \{Q_{11} + Q_{22} - 2Q_{12} + 4Q_{66}\}/8 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

and the reduced stiffness terms are calculated from the material properties:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{11} &= E_1/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{12} &= \nu_{12}E_2/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{22} &= E_2/(1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}) \\ Q_{66} &= G_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Non-dimensional parameters for coupled laminates

The calculation of the non-dimensional coupling stiffness parameters is readily demonstrated for the 8-ply laminate with stacking sequence $[\mathbf{O}/\pm/-/\mathbf{O}/+/\pm]_T$, where the coupling stiffness terms,

$$\mathbf{B}_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^n Q'_{ij}(z_k^2 - z_{k-1}^2)/2 \quad (9)$$

may be written in sequence order for the 8 individual plies, where z , representing the distance from the laminate mid-plane, is expressed here in terms of the uniform ply thickness t :

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{B}_{ij} &= \{Q'_{ij\mathbf{O}}((-3t)^2 - (-4t)^2) + Q'_{ij+}((-2t)^2 - (-3t)^2) + Q'_{ij-}((-t)^2 - (-2t)^2) + \\ &Q'_{ij-}((0)^2 - (-t)^2) + Q'_{ij\mathbf{O}}((t)^2 - (0)^2) + Q'_{ij+}((2t)^2 - (t)^2) + \\ &Q'_{ij+}((3t)^2 - (2t)^2) + Q'_{ij-}((4t)^2 - (3t)^2)\}/2 \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where subscripts $i, j = 1, 2, 6$.

The bending stiffness contribution from the angle plies is therefore:

$$\mathbf{B}_{ij+} = 3t^2/2 \times Q'_{ij+} \quad (11)$$

$$B_{ij-} = 3t^2/2 \times Q'_{ij-} \quad (12)$$

and for cross-ply:

$$B_{ij_0} = -6t^2/2 \times Q'_{ij_0} \quad (13)$$

$$B_{ij_{\bullet}} = 0 \quad (14)$$

These bending stiffness terms can be written in alternative form:

$$B_{ij+} = \chi_+ t^2/4 \times Q'_{ij+} \quad (15)$$

$$B_{ij-} = \chi_- t^2/4 \times Q'_{ij-} \quad (16)$$

and

$$B_{ij_0} = \chi_0 t^2/4 \times Q'_{ij_0} \quad (17)$$

respectively, where $\chi_+ = 6$, $\chi_- = 6$ and $\chi_0 = -12$

EQUIVALENT FULLY ISOTROPIC LAMINATES

The fully isotropic laminate, or **FIL**, offers the concept of a benchmark stacking sequence configuration, against which all laminates (coupled or uncoupled) may be characterized. However, previous work has shown that for thin laminates, with up to 21 plies, these so called benchmark configurations exist only for 18-ply laminates.

The concept of an Equivalent **FIL**, with any number of plies, must therefore be adopted. The benchmark configuration is now replaced by a set of stiffness properties for the Equivalent **FIL**, for which no physical stacking sequence configuration exists. The stiffness properties for the Equivalent **FIL** are readily obtained¹⁰ from the laminate invariants of Eqs. (7), expressed in terms of their isotropic material counterparts, where $E_1 = E_2$, $\nu_{12} = \nu_{21}$, etc:

$$E_{Iso} = 2(1 + \nu_{Iso})G_{Iso} = U_1(1 - \nu_{Iso}^2) \quad (18)$$

where

$$\nu_{Iso} = U_4/U_1 \quad (19)$$

and

$$G_{Iso} = U_5 \quad (20)$$

The Young's modulus, E_{Iso} , and Poisson ratio, ν_{Iso} , and shear modulus, G_{Iso} , are the equivalent isotropic material properties of a composite laminate of thickness, H , corresponding to the total number of plies, n , of uniform thickness, t , and from which the equivalent isotropic stiffness properties for laminates with any number of plies then follows:

$$A_{Iso} = A_{11} = A_{22} = E_{Iso}H/(1 - \nu_{Iso}^2) = U_1H \quad (21)$$

$$A_{12} = \nu_{Iso}A_{11} \quad (22)$$

$$A_{66} = U_5H \quad (23)$$

The bending stiffness elements follow from:

$$D_{Iso} = E_{Iso}H^3/(1 - \nu_{Iso}^2)/12 = U_1H^3/12 \quad (24)$$

For a typical carbon-fiber/epoxy material with Young's moduli $E_1 = 131.0\text{GPa}$ and $E_2 = 11.2\text{GPa}$, shear modulus $G_{12} = 6.55\text{GPa}$ and Poisson ratio $\nu_{12} = 0.28$, lamina thickness $t = 0.1397\text{mm}$ and **FIL** stacking sequence $NV 1071: [+/-2/\text{O}_3/+2/\text{O}/-/+2/-3/\text{O}_2/+]$ _T, the Equivalent **FIL** expressions in Eqs. (21) – (24) are readily verified as those presented below. For thermal expansion coefficients $\alpha_1 = -6.3 \times 10^{-8}$ and $\alpha_2 = 2.55 \times 10^{-5}$, the equivalent isotropic coefficient, $\alpha_{\text{Iso}} (= \alpha_1 = \alpha_2) = 2.40528 \times 10^{-6}$.

$$[\mathbf{A}] = \begin{bmatrix} 145,220 & 42,718 & 0 \\ & 145,220 & 0 \\ \text{Sym.} & & 51,249 \end{bmatrix} \text{N/mm and } [\mathbf{D}] = \begin{bmatrix} 76,519 & 22,509 & 0 \\ & 76,519 & 0 \\ \text{Sym.} & & 27,005 \end{bmatrix} \text{N.mm}$$

The bonding of a Gold outer layer, with Young's modulus $E = 78.0\text{GPa}$, Poisson ratio $\nu_{12} = 0.44$ and thickness $t = 0.00025\text{mm}$, to one surface of this **FIL** substrate, results in a modification to these stiffness terms, i.e $A_{11} = A_{22} = 145,240$, $A_{12} = 42,728$, $A_{66} = 51,256$ and $D_{11} = D_{22} = 76,557$, $D_{12} = 22,526$, $D_{66} = 27,016$, together with additional coupling matrix terms, i.e. $B_{11} = B_{22} = -12$, $B_{12} = -8$, $B_{66} = -2$. Figure 1 illustrates the free thermal contraction response, corresponding to a temperature reduction of 130°C , for a hipped spherical cap with and without a Gold surface layer (with side lengths $\ell = 1570\text{mm}$, with the shell mid-plane surface defined by $z = 2.085 \times 10^{-4}\{x(\ell - x) + y(\ell - y)\}$ and a square flat plate of equal dimensions with a Gold surface layer.

Figure 1 –Displacement arising from free thermal contraction of a fully isotropic laminate forming a: (a) hipped spherical cap ($z_{\text{max}} = 0.078\text{mm}$). Comparative response of a fully isotropic laminate substrate with Gold surface layer for a: (d) hipped spherical cap ($z_{\text{max}} = 0.093\text{mm}$) and; (c) flat plate ($z_{\text{max}} = 0.418\text{mm}$).

Search Strategy for approximate FILs

Grédiac⁸ suggests that **FILs** may not necessarily lead to the elimination of coupling behaviour any more than those of the approximate **FILs** when fibre alignment tolerances in the manufacturing process are taken into consideration. Indeed, the method presented herein considers only integer ply angles for the determination of sequences which fall within the desired tolerance: set to minimise orthotropic and twisting distortions.

Laminates are assessed in terms of the root sum square values of the membrane, coupling and flexural lamination parameters:

$$\xi_{\text{RSS}}^A = \sqrt{(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2 + \xi_3^2 + \xi_4^2)} \quad (25)$$

$$\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{B}} = \sqrt{(\xi_5^2 + \xi_6^2 + \xi_7^2 + \xi_8^2)} \quad (26)$$

$$\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}} = \sqrt{(\xi_9^2 + \xi_{10}^2 + \xi_{11}^2 + \xi_{12}^2)} \quad (27)$$

which are themselves then expressed as a root sum square value:

$$\xi_{\text{RSS}} = \sqrt{\{(\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{A}})^2 + (\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{B}})^2 + (\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}})^2\}} \quad (28)$$

For the purposes of approximation to the equivalent **FIL**, values of ξ_{RSS} are assessed on a scale of 0 to 1, which defines the absolute limits of the individual lamination parameters. Hence a proximity to the **FIL** of 1% is defined as $\xi_{\text{RSS}} = 0.01$.

Results and Discussion

Earlier work by Paradies³ on the assessment of laminate configurations for use in optical mirrors, presented polar plots giving only qualitative information on the variation of A_{11} and D_{11} , with respect to material-axis alignment; the **A**, **B** and **D** matrices were presented only for the axis-aligned laminate. Providing quantitative results for all A_{ij} and D_{ij} terms, normalised against the equivalent **FIL**, results in a plot from which it is difficult to assess the magnitude of variation, for this laminate. Higher fidelity is achieved by an alternative form of polar plot showing instead the magnitude of the error (%) with respect to the equivalent **FIL**. The 16-ply double-angle **FOL** polar plots for laminate stacking sequence $[\pm 27/\pm 74]_s/[\mp 27/\mp 74]_s$, which is of the form $[\pm\alpha/\pm\beta]_s/[\mp\alpha/\mp\beta]_s$, is illustrated in Fig. 2. This configuration is derived from the $(\pi/4)$ **EIL** sequence AC 30: $[+/-/\bigcirc/\bullet/\bullet/\bigcirc/-/+/-/+/\bullet/\bigcirc/\bigcirc/\bullet/+/-]_T$; However, the **EIL** properties are lost in achieving approximate bending isotropy, i.e. when symbols $+/-$ correspond to $(\pm)27^\circ$ and symbols \bigcirc/\bullet correspond to $(\pm)74^\circ$, respectively. A carpet plot for $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{A}}$ reveals that the minima ($\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{A}} = 1.23\%$) occur at $\pm\alpha = \pm 23^\circ$ or $\pm 68^\circ$ and $\pm\beta = \pm 68^\circ$ or $\pm 23^\circ$, respectively. By contrast, $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}} = 0.7\%$ at $\pm\alpha = \pm 27^\circ$ or $\pm 63^\circ$ and $\pm\beta = \pm 74^\circ$ or $\pm 16^\circ$, respectively, as illustrated in Fig. 2(c).

Figure 2 – (a) A_{ij} polar plot and; (b) D_{ij} polar plot, corresponding to stacking sequence $[\pm 27/\pm 74]_s/[\mp 27/\mp 74]_s$ after Paradies³. Carpet plot of (c) $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}} = \sqrt{(\xi_9^2 + \xi_{10}^2 + \xi_{11}^2 + \xi_{12}^2)}$ for fully uncoupled 16-ply $(\pi/4)$ **EIL** sequence AC 30 (after Reference 2).

The root sum square of the flexural lamination parameters, $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}} = \sqrt{(\xi_9^2 + \xi_{10}^2 + \xi_{11}^2 + \xi_{12}^2)}$, for the 15-ply laminate AC 1: $[+/\bigcirc/\bullet/-_2/\bullet/\bigcirc/\bullet_2/\bigcirc/+_2/\bigcirc/\bullet/-]_T$ derived previously², is also shown in the form of a carpet plot in Fig. 3(a). $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}} = 1.414$ when angle-ply symbols, $+/-$, correspond to $(\pm)0^\circ$ or $(\pm)90^\circ$ and cross-ply symbols, \bigcirc/\bullet , correspond to $(\pm)0^\circ$ or $(\pm)90^\circ$, respectively. By contrast, a **FIL** corresponds to $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^{\text{D}} =$

0. Approximate bending isotropy ($\leq 1\%$, or $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^D \leq 0.01$) is achieved for two angle ply combinations i.e. when symbols $+/-$ correspond to $(\pm)66^\circ$ or $(\pm)24^\circ$ and symbols \bigcirc/\bullet correspond to $(\pm)21^\circ$ or $(\pm)69^\circ$, respectively. However, the membrane and flexural stiffness properties have become coupled, i.e. an $A_F B_0 D_F$ laminate¹¹, in what is now an unbalanced laminate; the cross plies (\bigcirc/\bullet) of the original **FOL** configuration (*AC 1*) have become a second set of angle plies, giving $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^A = \sqrt{(\xi_1^2 + \xi_2^2 + \xi_3^2 + \xi_4^2)} = 0.2$, or 20%.

Figure 3 – (a) Carpet plot of $\xi_{\text{RSS}}^D = \sqrt{(\xi_9^2 + \xi_{10}^2 + \xi_{11}^2 + \xi_{12}^2)}$ for fully uncoupled 15-ply laminate *AC 1*: $[+/\bigcirc/\bullet/-_2/\bullet/\bigcirc/\bullet_2/\bigcirc/+_2/\bigcirc/\bullet/-]_T$, illustrating points of approximate bending isotropy ($\leq 1\%$), i.e. when symbols $+/-$ correspond to $(\pm)66^\circ$ or $(\pm)24^\circ$ and \bigcirc/\bullet to $(\pm)21^\circ$ or $(\pm)69^\circ$, respectively; (b) A_{ij} polar plot and; (c) D_{ij} polar plot.

Figure 4 illustrates out-of-plane (z) response, due to free thermal contraction of a number of competing laminate configurations in the literature. Figure 4(a) represents the 16-ply double-angle **FOL** after Paradies³ ($z_{\text{max}} = 0.056\text{mm}$), whereas Fig. 4(b) represents the coupled 15 ply *AC 1* laminate of Fig. 3. The deformation, $z_{\text{max}} = 0.078\text{mm}$, of the 12-ply equivalent **FIL** offers a comparison to the 12-layer multi-angle-ply approximate **FILs** of Grédiac⁸ and Vannucci⁹, illustrated in Fig. 4(c) and (d), respectively. Note that deformations are scaled ($\times 10^2$). The deformation illustrated in Fig. 4(d) may be contrasted against the polar plots for this laminate, given in Fig. 5.

Figure 4 – illustrating out-of-plane (z) response due to free thermal contraction of: (a) 16-ply double-angle **FOL** after Paradies³; (b); coupled 15 ply *AC 1* laminate of Fig. 3 (c) 12-layer multi-angle-ply approximate **FIL** after Grédiac⁸ ($z_{\text{max}} = 1.432\text{mm}$) and; (d) 12-layer multi-angle-ply approximate **FIL** after Vannucci⁹ ($z_{\text{max}} = 2.961\text{mm}$).

Ridgway and Barr¹² suggest that the conic constant of primary mirrors must have the value 1.0000 ± 0.0005 in order to function correctly with any secondary mirror meeting the conic constant requirement. This check has not yet been applied to the laminate configurations presented herein, however, Fig. 4(a) represents a degree of thermal distortion that is claimed to be acceptable³ for use in optical mirrors.

Figure 5 – Polar plots for the 12 layer multi-angle-ply laminate derived in [9] for: (a) A_{ij} ; (b) B_{ij} and; (c) D_{ij} .

Concluding remarks

Coupling between in- and out-of-plane behaviour has been considered in the development of approximate fully isotropic laminate or **FILs**. The search strategy adopted may also have practical relevance in the assessment of manufacturing tolerances with respect to fibre angle misalignment. Approximate **FILs** have been shown to be readily derived if the concept of non-standard or multiple angle-ply orientations with residual B-matrix (coupling) terms are acceptable. In such cases however, care must be exercised when assessing the behaviour of laminate based on its stiffness properties.

References

1. York, C. B., “Approximations for isotropic composite laminate configurations,” *Proc. 26th International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences Congress*, Anchorage, Alaska, ICAS Paper 2008-7.3.1, 14-19 Sept. 2008.
2. York, C. B., “Characterization of non-symmetric forms of fully orthotropic laminates,” *AIAA Journal of Aircraft*, In Press.
3. Paradies, R., “Designing quasi-isotropic laminates with respect to bending,” *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 56, 1996, pp. 461-472.
4. Paradies, R., and Hertwig M., “Shape control of adaptive composite reflectors,” *Composites: Part B*, Vol. 30, 1999, pp 65-78.
5. Kim, K-P., and Hale, D., “Design of directionally uniform extensional and flexural stiffness in quasi-isotropic laminates,” *Proc 49th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conf.*, Schaumburg, Illinois, AIAA Paper 2008-1749, 7-10 Apr. 2008.
6. Kim, K-P., and Hale, D., “Analysis of surface deformation due to thermal load on circular quasi-isotropic laminate mirrors,” *Proc 49th AIAA/ASME/*

ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics, and Materials Conf., Schaumburg, Illinois, AIAA Paper 2008-2185, 7-10 Apr. 2008.

7. Fukunaga, H., "On isotropic laminate configurations," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 24, 1990, pp. 519-535.
8. Grédiac, M., "A procedure for designing laminated plates with required stiffness properties, Application to thin quasi-isotropic quasi-homogeneous uncoupled laminates," *Journal of Composite Materials*, Vol. 33, No. 20, 1998, pp. 1939-1956.
9. Vannucci, P., "Designing the elastic properties of laminates as an optimization problem: a unified approach based on polar tensor invariants," *Journal of Structural and Multidisciplinary Optimisation*, Vol. 31, 2006, pp. 378-387.
10. Tsai, W. T. and Hahn, H. T., "Introduction to Composite Materials," Technomic Publishing Co. Inc., Lancaster, 1980.
11. "Stiffnesses of laminated plates", Engineering Sciences Data Unit, Rept. ESDU 94003, London 1994.
12. Ridgway, S.T., and Barr, L., "Telescope Primary Mirror Optical Requirements," Center for High Angular Resolution Astronomy, TR 15, California, 1995.